

Studies in Silicic Acid Gels. Part I. The Time of Setting of Gels.

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Fleming (*Z. Physik*, 1902, **41**, 427) prepared the silicic acid gel by mixing a solution of sodium silicate with different concentrations of sulphuric and nitric acids and found that the time of set of the gel was a minimum when the mixtures of the silicate and the acids were slightly alkaline. He considered the gel as set when the vessel containing the mixtures could be inverted without the gel flowing out.

Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, **22**, 510) prepared the gel by mixing solutions of sodium silicate with solutions of phosphoric, acetic, citric and tartaric acids of varying concentrations and found that the time of set of the gel was a minimum at two concentrations of the acids, one being very low and the other very high. Fells and Firth (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 241) using solutions of hydrochloric acid and sodium silicate found that the gel set in minimum time when the mixture was just alkaline and when the concentration of the acid was 10N.

Bhatnagar and Mathur (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, **30**, 368) were able to prepare very good gels by mixing solutions of ammonium acetate and sodium silicate. In the following, a systematic study of the formation of silicic acid gels by the latter method has been made, when the concentrations of the solutions of ammonium acetate and sodium silicate are gradually varied, and an attempt has been made to obtain some definite knowledge of the factors which control the time of setting of the gel.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Solutions.

A large quantity of Merck's dry sodium silicate (E. P. crystals) was kept in contact with distilled water for a period of two or three days. When a clear supernatant liquid was obtained,

it was twice filtered and stocked in a well-stoppered flask. Such a solution could keep undecomposed for a period of over three months. The strength of the sodium silicate was determined by estimating the silica content of this solution, and the other solutions required for the investigation were prepared by diluting the above. The strength of the different solutions has been expressed in grams of SiO_2 per 100 c.c.

Gels with Neutral Ammonium Acetate.

The neutral ammonium acetate obtained from British Drug House, Ltd. on analysis, gave ammonia and acetic acid in the proportion required by theory. The times of setting of the various gels were measured by Fleming's method (*loc. cit.*) and the results obtained are described in Tables I-VII.

TABLE I.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 0.493$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.			
Concentration of NH_4Ac :	8	10	21 per cent.
Time of setting (mins.) :	12	5	2 Ppt.

TABLE II.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 0.985$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.					
Concentration of NH_4Ac :	5	6	8	10	21 per cent.
Time of setting :	11'30"	4'50"	3'30"	1'20"	Ppt. (No firm gel)

In the above two cases where the concentration of silica is comparatively low, the gels formed are very flimsy and a little tilting of the test tube disturbs the gel structure and it begins to synerise.

TABLE III.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 1.97$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.						
Concentration of NH_4Ac :	4	5	6	8	10	21 per cent.
Time of setting :	20'	4'30"	2'	55"	10"	Inst. ppt.

TABLE IV.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 3.3$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.

Concentration of NH_4Ac :	4	4½	5	6	8	10	21 per cent.
Time of setting :	50'	12'	5'10"	1'40"	35"	Inst. ppt.	Flocks.

TABLE V.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 3.94$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.

Concentration of NH_4Ac :	4	4½	5	6	8	10 per cent.
Time of setting :	72'	18'	6'50"	2'	40"	Inst. gel.

TABLE VI.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4.92$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.

Concentration of NH_4Ac :	2.5	4	5	6	8	10 per cent.
Time of setting :	25 days	5 hrs.	10'	12'	2'30"	45" Inst. ppt.

TABLE VII.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 6.6$ per cent. Reaction alkaline.

Concentration NH_4Ac :	2.5	5	6	8	10 per cent.
Time of setting :	More than 25 days	45'	4'40"	50"	1"

The time of setting of these gels decreases as the concentration of ammonium acetate is increased up to a certain concentration only. Higher concentrations give no gels but flocculent precipitates. Also all the gels are alkaline to litmus and no minimum value of the time of set is observed as in the case of gels obtained from sodium silicate and acids.

But the behaviour of acidic ammonium acetate on the time of setting of silicic acid gels has been found to be different from the neutral one,

Gels with Acidic Ammonium Acetate.

A sample of ammonium acetate which was acidic was found to contain about 30 per cent. free acetic acid.

Equal volumes of this ammonium acetate were mixed with solutions of sodium silicate of different strengths and the time of setting was measured in the first instance by Fleming's method.

It was, however, observed in the case of these and the foregoing experiments that the method of measuring the time of set was not quite satisfactory as the gelling substance had to be frequently disturbed.

The criterion of setting of a gel, defined as a body which has a form or shape and is solid-like in appearance, should be the attainment of that form or shape, which occurs when its elasticity reaches a specific value. Hatschek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, **39**, 300) from a study of the shear moduli of sols and emulsions has shown that their elasticity is directly related to their viscosity. The viscosity of a suspension is known to depend upon the number of particles, their electric charge, degree of hydration and their specific nature.

Light scattered by any disperse system depends upon the size of the particles and the degree of dispersity. If a system is, therefore, undergoing a change in hydration and dispersity, scattering of light will change in the same way as the viscosity and hence its elasticity. It appears, therefore, that the method of scattering of light can be used as a correct criterion for determining the time of setting of the gel. This will have a further advantage of indicating the changes in the condition of the gel particles during the process of gelation and on changes in the silica content of the mixture.

Fells and Firth (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, **23**, 623) suggested that the setting point of the gel should be that at which the pressure required to blow or suspend a bubble of air or of mercury or of chloroform coloured with iodine, through the gel-forming mixture reaches a maximum value. In this method the gel-forming mixtures are disturbed, whereby the setting process is considerably altered. The method of scattering of light, pointed out above, obviates this difficulty.

The method involving the variation in the intensity of the scattered light has also been used by Mardles (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, **18**, 318) in the study of the sol-gel transformation of gels of cellulose

acetate. Arisz (*Kolloidchem. Beihefte*, 1915, 7, 14) working with glycerol sols of gelatine also employed the same method and measured the intensity of the scattered light by a photographic method.

In the present investigation light from a lamp burning at 230 volts and 1.03 amps. was focussed for a parallel beam by a condenser of a long focal length. The parallel beam was then allowed to pass through a cell containing water to remove most of the heat rays and ultra-violet rays. This was then allowed to fall on a rectangular cell made of optically correct glass, containing the gel-forming mixture. The intensity of transmitted light was measured by means of a linear thermopile attached to a Broca galvanometer. The deflection of the galvanometer was measured on a scale placed at about one meter from it. The current passing through the lamp was adjusted to the same value, at each observation by means of a variable resistance, and the distance between the light source and the various cells was kept fixed throughout the whole investigation.

Equal volumes of ammonium acetate and sodium silicate were mixed thoroughly in a test-tube and transferred to the optical cell. The stop-watch was simultaneously started and the deflection of the galvanometer was measured at regular intervals of time. The results obtained are given in the following tables in which the symbols used represent:—

T = time after mixing the solutions, in minutes ;

D = deflection differences ($D_1 - D_t$, where D_1 is the initial and D_t the deflection at time t), in mms

In all the mixtures examined, the concentration of ammonium acetate used was more than the equivalent quantity of the sodium silicate solution used.

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 2$ per cent.

Concentrations of ammonium acetate.

4 per cent.		6 per cent.		8 per cent.	
T .	D .	T .	D .	T .	D .
0.5	0	0.5	0	1	0
1.5	0.5	1	5	2	0
3	2.5	1.5	11	5	1
5	6.5	2	18	7	1.5

It will be seen from these tables that in each case the deflection of the galvanometer decreases as the time increases, at first rapidly and then slowly and more slowly until it reaches an almost constant value. These results have been plotted with deflection as ordinates against time as abscissa and typical curves are shown in Fig. 1. The

Fig. 1.

curves are sometimes sigmoid in shape there being a point of inflexion in the curve, after which there is a steady decline in the rate of change and point to the auto-catalytic nature of the reaction. The time when the deflection has become almost constant, *i.e.*, when the curve shows a tendency of running parallel to the time-axis, is read from the curve and taken as the time of setting of the gel.

These times of setting have been compared with those obtained by Fleming's method under similar conditions and are shown in the following tables. The reaction of these mixtures towards litmus has also been given in the last columns of these tables.

TABLE XI.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 2$ per cent.

Conc. of NH_4Ac .	Time (Fleming's method).	Time (Optical method).	Reaction.
4 per cent.	7'	10'	Alkaline
5	2'40"	6'30"	"
6	1'45"	3	"
8	12'30"	18'	Acidic
10	90'	—	"

TABLE XII.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 3$ per cent.

Conc. of NH_4Ac .	Time (Fleming's method).	Time (Optical method.)	Reaction.
4 per cent.	9'30"	14'	Alkaline.
5	2'30"	5'30"	"
6	1'	2'	"
	0'25"		"
10	0'25"	1'	...
12	5'	8'	Acidic.
16	60'	—	Acidic.

TABLE XIII.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4$ per cent.

Conc. of NH_4Ac .	Time (Fleming's method).	Time (Optical method).	Reaction.
4 per cent.	22'30"	35'	Alkaline.
5	3'	7'	"
6	1'	2'	"
8	10"	—	—
18	5'	9'	Acidic.
20	19'	24'	"

The foregoing results show that the time of setting of the gel obtained by the optical method is always higher than that obtained by Fleming's method. This is, as was expected, as the latter method depends only upon the attainment of a certain viscosity by the mixture. As the gel begins to set, the viscosity of the mixture increases continuously until after some time it reaches a sufficiently high value to prevent the flowing out of the gel. At this point, however, the viscosity may not have reached its maximum value, as the size of the particles which contributes a lot to viscosity, still continues to

increase. Bachmann (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 73, 125) in an ultra-microscopic study of the structure of the jellies observed that the size of the particles increased during the ageing of the gel, and for systems of low concentrations, there was a gradual formation of separate flocculent particles or aggregates of sub-microns.

It will be further seen from the Tables (XI-XIII) that the time of setting of the gels depends both upon the concentration of silica and ammonium acetate. With a particular solution of sodium silicate and increasing concentrations of ammonium acetate, the time of set of the gels varies as shown in Fig. 2. On plotting $\log C$ against $\log T$, C being the concentration of ammonium acetate and T the time of set of the gel, two intersecting straight lines are obtained. The equation to the original curve can, therefore, be written as

$$(t - \alpha c^n)(t - \beta c^{-m}) = 0$$

where α , β , n and m are constants.

Fig. 2.

All mixtures set in a minimum time when they are slightly alkaline or neutral to litmus and the value of this minimum time is smaller, the greater is the silica content of the mixtures (cf. Flem-

ing, Fells and Firth). Highly alkaline and highly acidic mixtures take a long time to set.

The behaviour of the acidic ammonium acetate is different from that of the neutral one in that the former gives a minimum in the concentration-time of setting curves. Also, the reaction of all the gels obtained from the neutral ammonium acetate is alkaline but the acid one gives alkaline, neutral, or acid reaction depending upon the concentration of the ammonium acetate used. This indicates that the peculiar behaviour of acidic ammonium acetate is due to the presence of free acetic acid in it and that the variation in the time of setting depends upon the H- and OH-ion concentration of the mixtures.

Further examination of the gels obtained from acidic ammonium acetate showed that they differed in appearance from each other according as they were prepared from high or low concentrations of ammonium acetate. Differences in the structure of gels prepared from widely different concentrations, have been observed by Hardy (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1900, **4**, 254) in systems of agar in water and gelatine in aqueous alcohol. The gels obtained in the present investigation can be classified into two types: (a) those which appear a bit opaque in transmitted light, (b) those which are transparent. The differences in the optical properties of these gels can be seen from the following results taken from Tables VIII-X.

TABLE XIV.

Absorption of Light in Terms of Galvanometer Deflection when the Gels set.

Conc. of $\text{NH}_4\text{Ac.}$	Concentration of silica.		
	2 per cent.	3 per cent.	4 per cent.
4 per cent.	18.5 mm.	22 mm.	27.5 mm.
5	—	27	28.5
8	15	—	—
12	—	22	—
18	—	—	16.5
20	—	—	15.5

Also, by reflected light (a) type gels appear more bluish than the (b) type ones.

It will be seen from the above table and Tables XI-XIII that mixtures which are even slightly acidic are more transparent than the alkaline ones. It seems, therefore, that the influence of the medium is an important factor in determining the transparency of the gels. The transparency of a disperse system depends upon the degree of dispersion and hence it appears that large aggregates are formed in alkaline mixtures than in acidic ones. The inference that the molecular aggregates formed in the gels from acidic mixtures are comparatively smaller than those from the alkaline ones, is similar to the observation of Linder and Picton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, **61**, 154), who found that no Tyndall-cone is shown by the undialysed sol of silicic acid in the presence of large concentrations of hydrochloric acid and concluded that molecular aggregates of sufficient size to scatter light, are not formed in these mixtures.

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